

Synthesis, characterization and biological evaluations of heterobinuclear complexes of Cu^{II} and Ni^{II} Schiff base of ethylenediamine and *o*-hydroxyacetophenone with alkali metal salts of *o*-nitrophenol

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Manuscript received 12 November 2016, revised 29 April 2017, accepted 15 May 2017

Abstract : Novel heterobinuclear alkali metal complexes have been synthesized by the interaction of stable Cu^{II} and Ni^{II} metal chelate of ethylenediamine and *o*-hydroxyacetophenone with alkali metal salts. The structures of these complexes have been discussed on the basis of elemental analysis, IR and UV-Vis spectral data and magnetic measurement. The Cu^{II} and Ni^{II} metal chelates act as ligand and coordination towards alkali metal salts takes place through phenolic oxygen atom. The complexes have square planar geometry and there is no change in the stereochemistry of the Ni²⁺ and Cu²⁺ in the adducts and their metal chelate. The biological analyses of some of heterobinuclear complexes are assayed and demonstrated a general inhibitory effect.

Keywords : Cu^{II} and Ni^{II} Schiff's base, heterobinuclear alkali metal complexes, antimicrobial studies, MIC.

Introduction

Schiff bases derived from the reaction of aldehyde or ketone and amines represent an important series of widely studied organic ligand. In the recent years coordination compounds of biologically active ligands¹⁻³ have receive much attention. A number of Schiff base complexes have been tested for antimicrobial activities and they have been found antibacterial^{4,5} and antifungal⁵⁻⁷ activities. Binucleating Schiff bases have been extensively used for the preparation of homo and heterobinuclear complexes^{8,9}. We have reported the synthesis, characterization and biological studies of number of binuclear Schiff base metal complex^{10,11}. The present investigation deals with the synthesis and characterization of heterobinuclear alkali metal complexes of Cu^{II} and Ni^{II} Schiff base. The bonding between the *N,N'*-ethylene-bis(2-hydroxyacetophenoniminato)metal(II) complex and the alkali metal is most likely to occur by dative bonding via the two phenolic oxygen atoms of the ligand which has been supported by the infrared, electronic absorption spectra and magnetic studies of the adducts. The minimum inhibitory concentrations (MIC) of the prepared complexes show

the antimicrobial effectiveness.

Results and discussion

The analytical and physical results of metal chelate and its binuclear complexes having general formula M(ohap.ed) and M(ohap.ed)M'L (where M = Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}, ohap.ed = Schiff base of 1,2-ethylenediamine and *o*-hydroxyacetophenone, M' = Li or Na or K and L = deprotonated *o*-nitrophenol) shown in Table 1.

The Cu^{II} and Ni^{II} metal chelate, and their alkali metal adducts are intensively coloured solid and stable at room temperature. The complexes are generally soluble in methanol, acetone, benzene and DMF but insoluble in water. The elemental analyses data concur well with the planned formula for the binuclear complexes. The observed molar conductance (1.8–3.1 Ω⁻¹ cm² mol⁻¹) of all the metal complexes in 10⁻³ molar in DMF solution at 30 (±0.5) °C are suggested the non-electrolytic¹² nature of these complexes.

Infrared spectra :

The relevant IR spectra and their assignment are shown in the Table 2. The IR spectra of heterobinuclear complexes in comparison with the metal complex as

Table 1. Analytical and molar conductance data of the complexes

Complexes	Colour	M.p./Dec. temp. (°C)	Molar cond. ($\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$)	Elemental analysis (%) :					Yield (%)
				Found (Calcd.)					
ML				C	H	N	M	M'	
Cu(ohap.ed)	Deep red	245d							71.00
Cu(ohap.ed).LiL	Pale rose	280d	2.1	57.25 (57.31)	4.31 (4.38)	8.32 (8.36)	12.55 (12.64)	1.37 (1.39)	77.11
Cu(ohap.ed).NaL	Pale rose	285d	3.1	55.45 (55.54)	4.21 (4.24)	8.01 (8.10)	12.15 (12.25)	4.41 (4.44)	71.36
Cu(ohap.ed).KL	Pale rose	292d	2.6	53.75 (53.88)	4.10 (4.12)	7.83 (7.86)	11.80 (11.88)	7.23 (7.30)	79.51
Ni(ohap.ed)	Brownish orange	280d							75.5
Ni(ohap.ed).LiL	Brownish orange	265d	2.4	57.78 (57.87)	4.38 (4.42)	8.36 (8.44)	11.76 (11.79)	1.38 (1.41)	74.34
Ni(ohap.ed).NaL	Yellowish orange	> 300	2.0	56.00 (56.06)	4.21 (4.28)	8.11 (8.18)	11.39 (11.43)	4.41 (4.48)	74.95
Ni(ohap.ed).KL	Yellowish orange	> 300	1.8	54.30 (54.37)	4.11 (4.15)	7.88 (7.93)	11.01 (11.08)	7.33 (7.36)	73.15

Table 2. Spectral data of metal chelate and their metal complexes

Compd.	Infrared spectra (cm^{-1})			UV-Vis spectra	μ_{eff} (B.M.)
	$\nu(\text{C-O})$ phenolic	$\nu(\text{M-N})$	$\nu(\text{M-O})$	λ (nm)	
Cu(ohap.ed)	1531	521	490	227, 270, 400, 653	1.50
Cu(ohap.ed).LiL	1537	560	470	228, 266, 347, 653	1.70
Cu(ohap.ed).NaL	1532	562	440	230, 232, 350, 652	1.74
Cu(ohap.ed).KL	1535	550	465	227, 260, 345, 653	1.73
Ni(ohap.ed)	1530	518	495	212, 246, 316, 390, 653	Dia.
Ni(ohap.ed).LiL	1590	565	460	207, 261, 340, 384, 653	Dia.
Ni(ohap.ed).NaL	1568	562	465	210, 285, 358, 386, 652	Dia.
Ni(ohap.ed).KL	1565	555	462	214, 280, 352, 389, 653	Dia.

ligand display certain changes which give an idea about the types of bonds and their structure. The disappearance in the spectra of metal complex as ligand of very sharp absorption peak (3500 cm^{-1} , ν_{OH}), indicate the deprotonation of phenolic proton on complex formation. The Cu(ohap.ed) and Ni(ohap.ed) and its binuclear alkali metal complexes show infrared bands at $1530\text{--}1590 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, this band may be due to the C-O stretching frequency in these compounds, rather than $\text{C}=\text{N}^{13}$. Comparison of the C-O infrared bands of binuclear alkali metal complexes of Cu(ohap.ed) and Ni(ohap.ed) to that of transition metals, show that they remain almost same. The metal complex as ligand exhibit the

$\nu_{\text{C-O}}$ (phenolic) ($1530\text{--}1531 \text{ cm}^{-1}$), which shifted towards higher energy side on complex formation, indicate the coordination through the phenolic oxygen¹⁴. The shift is expected due to maintenance of a ring current rising from electron delocalisation in chelating ring. The major shifts of $\nu_{\text{C-O}}$ (phenolic) to higher frequency by $\sim 60 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in complexes certainly show the presence of phenoxo bridge¹⁴⁻¹⁶. It is therefore suggested that the phenolic C-O link attached a considerable amount of partial double bond character in these complexes. This is what to be expected from the readiness with which these binuclear complexes were formed.

The IR bands of medium intensity in the far infrared region at 440–470 cm^{-1} and 550–565 cm^{-1} in the binuclear complexes tentatively assigned by $\nu_{\text{M-O}}$ and $\nu_{\text{M-N}}$ modes^{17,18}. These bands are not present in the ligand (ethylenediamine and *o*-hydroxyacetophenone) of the neutral transition metal chelates Cu(ohap.ed) and Ni(ohap.ed) at region 490–495 cm^{-1} and 518–521 cm^{-1} respectively. The above data confirm the coordination of oxygen atom of phenolic group and nitrogen atom of $-\text{NO}_2$ to the alkali metals in all the binuclear complexes.

Electronic spectra and magnetic studies :

The UV-Vis absorption spectra values of the maximum absorption wavelength (λ_{max}) are listed in Table 2. The neutral metal chelate and their binuclear complexes showed strong broad band in the range 207–316 nm are indicated the formation of $\pi-\pi^*$ transition in aromatic ring and C=N chromophore. The medium absorption band observed in the range 340–400 nm due to ligand to metal charge transfer transition and intense absorption peak appearing at ~ 653 nm in all the complexes corresponds to d-d transition^{19,21}. This assigned that square planar geometry of Cu^{II} and Ni^{II} with coordination number 4 and there is no changes in stereochemistry of the metal chelate and their binuclear complexes after adduct formation. The absence of band in the region 700–1200 nm of electronic spectra indicate that coordination number of Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} in the adducts have not been raised but it remains four with square planar structure.

Magnetic susceptibility measurements at room temperature of complexes give a magnetic moment value (Table 2) μ_{eff} of Cu(ohap.ed) is 1.5 B.M., correspond to the presence of one unpaired electron and square planar geometry with coordination number 4 and its adducts show magnetic moment values between 1.70 to 1.74 B.M. These results of μ_{eff} are attributed that the stereochemistry of Cu(ohap.ed) unit in the adducts almost remains same. The magnetic moment values of Ni(ohap.ed) and its adducts show very low value (approximately zero), which correspond to the diamagnetic nature and square planar geometry with coordination number 4.

Structure and bonding :

The bonding between the *N,N'*-ethylene-bis(2-hydroxyacetophenoniminato)metal(II) complex [M(ohap.ed)] and the alkali metal is most likely to occur by dative bonding via the two phenolic oxygen atoms of the ligand which has been supported by the IR and UV-Vis spectral data and magnetic properties. The structure and bonding of the newly prepared compounds by us of the general formula [M(ohap.ed).M'L] may have the structure shown in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Suggested structure for heterobinuclear complex.

Antimicrobial activity :

The heterobinuclear complexes were tested for their antibacterial activity against bacteria viz. *Escherichia coli*, *Staphylococcus aureus* and fungus viz. *Candida albicans* in DMF in the concentration range 25–200 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$. The minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) results of the some of the complexes are shown in Table 3 and Fig. 2. These observations show that most of the adducts of Ni(ohap.ed) and Cu(ohap.ed) have great degree of activity at higher concentration against test organism and also as the concentration of these adducts increases antimicrobial activity²² increase gradually. Better activities of some of the complexes as compared to the ligand can be explained by chelation theory²³. The theory explains that decrease in polarizability of the metal could enhance the lipophilicity of the complexes which leads to the breakdown of permeability of the cells resulting in interference with normal cell process.

Table 3. MIC values of the synthesized compounds

Compd.	Concn. ($\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$)	Percentage inhibition		
		<i>E. coli</i>	<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>C. albicans</i>
Ni(ohap.ed).KL	200	100	80	100
	100	100	58	100
	50	92	54	87
	25	87	35	83
Ni(ohap.ed).LiL	200	88	90	62
	100	85	86	55
	50	75	72	50
	25	72	55	48
Cu(ohap.ed).LiL	200	100	100	88
	100	100	100	85
	50	92	100	65
	25	88	87	55
Cu(ohap.ed).KL	200	100	100	100
	100	92	100	100
	50	86	90	90
	25	82	85	88
Chloramphenicol	200	96	92	95
	25	75	68	72

nitrogen were estimated by micro analytical method. Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} of the complexes were analyzed by EDTA titration after decomposition with nitric acid and sulphuric acid. Vibrating Sample Magnetometer was used to measure magnetic susceptibilities.

The Schiff base bis(2-hydroxyacetophenone-ethylenediamine) was prepared from *o*-hydroxyacetophenone and ethylenediamine by the refluxing in 2 : 1 molar proportion in ethanol for 0.5–1 h. The yellow Schiff base was filtered off, washed with ethanol and dried in oven. A solution of copper(II) acetate hydrate (2.0 g) or nickel(II) acetate tetrahydrate (2.5 g) in ethanol (15 ml) was added slowly with stirring to hot solution of the Schiff base (2.96 g). The solution, upon cooling, deposited deep red copper complex or the brownish orange nickel complex. These were filtered off, washed with ethanol and dried.

Heterobinuclear complexes containing Cu^{II} metal and alkali metal :

N,N'-Ethylene-bis(2-hydroxyacetophenoniminato)

Fig. 2. Antimicrobial efficiency of chemically synthesized compounds at conc. 25 μg per ml.

Experimental

Chemicals of AR grade have been used for synthesizing the compounds. Melting points were determined on electric melting point apparatus model T-1150. Molar conductivities were measured with the help of Systronic digital direct conductivity meter-306. IR spectra were recorded on FTIR spectrophotometer, Shimadzu model-8201PC in KBr phase. Electronic spectra were recorded on Perkin-Elmer Lambda 15 UVB VIS spectrophotometer. Carbon, hydrogen and

copper(II) [Cu(ohap.ed)] was taken in absolute alcohol in a conical flask and alkali metal salts of *o*-nitrophenol was added to it in 1 : 1 molar proportion. The mixture was refluxed on a hot plate at 75–80 °C with stirring for 1–1.5 h. The characteristic colour adducts were precipitated in hot condition, which was filtered, washed with absolute ethanol and dried.

Heterobinuclear complexes containing Ni^{II} metal and alkali metal :

N,N'-Ethylene-bis(2-hydroxyacetophenoniminato)

nickel(II) [Ni(ohap.ed)] was taken in absolute alcohol in a conical flask and alkali metal salts of *o*-nitrophenol was added to it in 1 : 1 molar proportion. The mixture was refluxed on a hot plate at 75–80 °C with stirring for 1–1.5 h. The characteristic colour adducts were precipitated in hot condition, which was filtered, washed thoroughly with absolute ethanol and dried.

Acknowledgement

Author is thankful to Director, IIT Kanpur and Director, CDRI Lucknow to provide instrumental facilities.

References

1. A. D. Naik, S. M. Annigeri, U. B. Gangadharmath, V. K. Ravankar, V. B. Mahale and V. K. Reddy, *Indian J. Chem.*, 2002, **41A**, 2046.
2. A. K. Sen, G. Singh, K. Singh, R. K. Noren, R. N. Handa and S. N. Dubey, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1997, **36A**, 891.
3. A. K. Sen, G. Singh, K. Singh, R. N. Handa, S. N. Dubey and P. J. Squattirito, *Proc. Indian Acad. Sci.*, 1998, **110**, 75.
4. A. S. Kabeer, M. A. Baseer and N. A. Mote, *Asian J. Chem.*, 2001, **13**, 496.
5. P. Piotr, H. Adam, P. Krystian, B. Bogumil and B. Franz, *Curr. Org. Chem.*, 2009, **13**, 124.
6. W. M. Singh and B. C. Dash, *Pesticides*, 1988, **22**, 33.
7. V. S. Jolly, M. Y. Dalvi and A. K. Srivastava, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1991, **68**, 513.
8. D. E. Fenton, U. Casellato, P. A. Vigato and M. Vidali, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1984, **95**, 187.
9. U. Casellato, P. A. Vigato, D. E. Fenton and M. Vidali, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1979, **8**, 199.
10. D. Prakash, Chandan Kumar, A. K. Gupta, S. Prakash and K. R. R. P. Singh, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2008, **85**, 252.
11. D. Prakash, Chandan Kumar and K. R. R. P. Singh, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2008, **85**, 371.
12. W. J. Geary, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1971, **7**, 81.
13. P. L. Teyessia and J. J. Charette, *Spectrochim. Acta*, 1963, **19**, 1407.
14. A. Z. El-Sonbati and M. A. Hefni, *Monat. Chem.*, 1993, **124**, 419.
15. A. Z. El-Sonbati, A. S. Al-Shihri and A. A. El-Bindary, *Spectrochimica Acta, Part A*, 2004, **60(A)**, 1763.
16. E. Sinn and C. N. Harris, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1969, **4**, 89.
17. K. Nakamoto, "Infrared and Raman Spectra of Inorganic and Coordination Compounds", John Wiley, New York, 1978.
18. R. A. Condrate and K. Nakamoto, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1965, **42**, 2590.
19. H. H. Jaffer and M. Orclin, "Theory and Application of UV Spectroscopy", Wiley, New York, 1962, 347.
20. M. Kato, K. Jmai, Y. Mutto and T. Tokii, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1966, **7**, 83.
21. P. Cheng, D. Liao, S. Yan, Z. Jiang and G. Wang, *Transition Met. Chem.*, 1996, **21**, 515.
22. Kiran Singh, Manjeet Singh Barwa and Parikshit Tyagi, *Eur. J. Med. Chem.*, 2006, **41**, 147.
23. Suparna Ghosh, Suman Malik, Bharti Jain and Mudit Gupta, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2012, **89**, 471.

